

MULTI-CORKING RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS.

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Abstract: In the case, the article today depends on the number of multi-storey residential buildings in the country and in the world. The historical solutions of multi-storey residents are given historical solutions.

Key words: Project, multi-storey building, design, easy conditions, beautification, accommodiary building

Accommodation is one of the people living in person or other animals as human or other animals live as human or other animals. Residence is diverse: from a simple hut to a system of complex devices. Permanent residents are called home in the living place. The social unit living in the house is called home, which is usually family, and in some cases any other social group, organization or single person.

The front view of the building

Residence - Residence, Seating of Shelter, Jobs. The house where the family lives, an environment where the family passes the household life. The accommodation was preparing to cook in primitive periods, wearing a dress. Homes The architecture is the most common structure of architects, and in many ways has determined the formation and development of other structures. The diversity of the outside and internal shapes, species and appearance of the residential forms, the nature of social relations, economic levels, degree of economic and national and national traditions has become complicated. Narrative forms of accommodation. is known from the tear of stone. The dwellings have risen to modern multi-storey houses since for centuries, since the ordinary shelter in nature. At the same time, the student formula has been provided by the form of form of architecture. During the stone, the gore, tent, cells serve as the position of housing (see primitive society). Man has also changed, and wooden houses have also changed, and wooden houses have also occurred in woodshed areas (wood, and housing on wetlands were built and built on fire. The climate is used from Nolitite in the field of Nolist, mud, suit bricks, gavalala, straw, using Neolithic times. Mobile TJS widespread in the lands of Asia and Africa. The tent (from the skin of the beast, fabric; in the January of Asia, Jeranians, Arabs), white house The Dashti was observed in areas with Eastern Europe. In northern Eskimos settlements are built in the skin and ice.

Following a stratification in society. Egypt is. In addition to the simplest home and huts of Rome and Greeks, as well as the artists, multifaceted centuries of the losers were built. Residence on the curderly pleased plain cities is still preserved in the cities of Western Europe. Eastern Slavic (at the same time Russia, Ukrainian, Belarus) and the territory are first common at the nearby peoples (letters, etc.) at the near future. The huts built by the clay and stone in the Caucasus peoples were distributed from stems, towerrelative multi-storey houses (mountainous Dagsus, etc.). In India, the accommodation has been printed on raw and baked brick, its roof flat, and the straw rejnish, it is printed on top of the steam. There were also houses with a silent wood or bamboo with straw mud. In East Asia (Maye. Pants. In China),

the straw, reed is suppressed on the roof over the vulture, raw brick wall. The places where there is a frequent earthquake and mostly cracked houses were built.

During the awakening, Italian cities in the cities of Italy (dous Palace of DOCs, etc. In the late 19th century - in early 20th century, developed in the 20th century had a significant impact on the construction of housing in other European countries. It then F. ubb, N.Shou and Ch. The architectural project, like Wowis, explained its environment, demonstrating its environment, climatic darkness, and building materials used, and construction materials used. In developed U.S. industry, such as Canada, the use of large standes produced in the accommodation industry has created great opportunities for the use of the same standard of housing. The workshop in Europe manifested in clear examples of taking into account a rational account of a series of integrated common household needs. Income Coding Houses, which is built in multiple families, in molten families, played an important role in the creation of opportunities and methods of architects to build a modern accommodation.

In developed European 20th century, new construction materials (metals, reinforced, etc.) were implemented in the construction of modern housing. The large number of houses that bring income as a result of population growth in cities was focused on the construction of the income. Multiled multidies consisting of modern constipation (water, sewer, gas, elevator, etc.) spread in the construction of accommodation. The first residences of the first residences in Uzbekistan were found in Togkorzin, Jilgula, Jonboskala, Dalvzintepa, Termez, Soarkalka, Tukezkalka. In construction, wood, mud, cotton, and gawal were used. The walls of the palace in Varacshash, Afrosiab, Childishtepa and others are decorated with Rayems, statues and fed embellishes. Cache in the 6-8th centuries, Sughd, Toharistan, Changaly, and Changhanon, Shosh was mainly built on irrigated lines. Credkles lived in areas around the city. The Turkic population living in ancient Turkestan pastures (UTOV, land, tent, hungry, Kapas, Favora, Favora, etc., etc.). According to the cane houses

installed in 2 or 4 wheeled carriers, the Turkish people who initially discovered the PLLOZDO BAKI and others say the Khorezmshah Kulgani Bahodirkhan said later. Sky houses Mil.av. It is also widely built in the 4th century. The tent, like Air, was built on the basis of wooden devices and fertilizers.

Multi-storey accommodation wall plan

The architecture of housing, built during the reign of Amir Temur, is distinguished by its luxury, the height of engineering science, richness in engineering decorations (see Amir Turur Gardens, the Oqsaroy. In historical sources, interesting information about palaces, bubbag and other is preserved.

Mahapla and guzars are formed in urban centers, and in them also built their luxurious abode in the same shops (Chorsu, Tim, mount). The dwellings are inner and plightish courtyards and are equipped with the position of the homeowner's owner. Hotels are decorated with unique national ornaments (shelf, orgum, shipi

vassaln, pond, wall patterns). Carpets, sheets, suzana, Sandah, promotions, are equipped with mahraki mahraki such as the table.

In old cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Shahrissabz, Kokand, Tashkent, are unique in a unique figure, the use of local building materials, all the ways to block the heat of the sun . The interest of houses is manifested through the courtyards, and on the street, the porch in front of the carved door and gate is seen. T.Jes cannot be imagined without a courtyard and porch (see turmurg, sitory Mohi kosa, nurullaboy palace, and b.).

In addition to the traditional accidents, 1-2 storey houses in Tashkent, Samarkand, Kagan, Andijan, and other cities, began construction of 1-2-way houses in the European style, along with traditional accommodation. The architectural appearances of these buildings seemed alien to local conditions. In the early 20th century, the early 20th, ordinary houses were built on the Railway Street in Tashkent (former Fiber Fast). Romanov and traders' palace, A.Polovsev House, Kokabka Simkhoev Houses, Kokaba Simxoev House and Kokaba, Kalontarov House and Kalokhoev House, Knakau Simkhoevs, built in Samarkand in partnership with V.S. Covalichevsky, V.S. Taneselman, and other local masters of other people. Since 1937, 4-5-storey residential buildings of the Jobs, then 9-story (1966) The construction of the assembly receptive settlements escalated. In rural areas, 2-storey cottages were built on the basis of the architectural project such as R.Abdurovov, A.Mahkamov, V. Kolomensky. The introduction of 3-4-storey houses in agriculture has caused considerable inconvenience to the population. In the 70s, new types of projects in the same standard were created in the 70s. Experimental accidents were built from 80 to 80s. Projects in 76, 146, 148, 176, 176 categories of housing in the cities were used to build large domestic growth (Chilanzar, Sergeli, Yunusabad, Sebzor, and others. But as these projects have a considerable convenience, they could not fully satisfy local needs and requirements of the residents. These needs

and requirements, mainly, were carried out mainly in 1-2-storey private accommodation.

The architectural architecture is classified at the moment, including on construction technology (large block, panel), built separately on the implementation technology (built separately), on the implementation of projects (individual, reorganizer), intermittent of apartment (galleries) on the floor (as gallery) on the layers (such as rigids), ownership of households (such as apartments), in the presence of the courtyard, the state property), more b. is divided according to aspects. Out of the city is distinguished by its simpler view.

Appearance of a multi-storey residential building

The most important qualities of accommodation are its comfort and beauty. They are provided with a voice of the architectural solution (different, sometimes interdependent distribution requirements, the full operation of the constructive and

fad qualities of construction materials). In the local settlements, decorations such as paintings, carving are widely used. In accommodation, equipment (Imumon), including Hot, while there is also a state of engineering, air conditioning, sewage, ventilation, air conditioning and other important importance. There are various furniture (tables, courses, soft furniture) gives rooms. Consumer for household appliances (refrigeration, televisions, computer) is expanding. Creating a lot of equipment is raised to the art level (ceremony, carpets, carpets, embroidery, etc.).

The Uzbek housing pays great attention to landscaping and water facilities. The link is allocated from one part of the courtyard or from a separate place. They are mainly grown in fruit, partially ornamental trees. Flowers are planted on the yard stage and is planted to him, Rayhon, Shoyiul. It previously had pure, drinking water led by almost every house's beaver. Some courses in the current courtyards are being built in a water basin (pools), fountains.

The Uzbek settlements are reflected in neighboring and neighborhood traditions, and the landlord has always made the height of the device with the consent of the unit of the device, with the consent of the neighbor. In addition, neighbor relations were identified and similar customs such as "Obraa", "afkiq".

New construction criteria and rules have been adopted in the architectural after the independence. The construction of individuals with state-story and cottage and cottage accommodation were widespread, including luxury ("elite) houses, including luxury (" elite) houses. The national and "European methods are widely used in the settlements, new construction technology and items are widely used.

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